

Statistics Netherlands' Person Network: improvements, expansions and applications

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Background

In 2020, Statistics Netherlands (Centraal Bureau voor de Statistiek, CBS) developed the Person Network (Persoonsnetwerk), which is a first version of a social network covering the entire Dutch population as of the reference date of 1 October 2018. The first pilot for of this work, covering only the information over 2014, was developed earlier through the ODISSEI Secure Supercomputer (OSSC). The Person Network is based on data from government records and is made up of five so-called network layers: family members, household members, neighbours, colleagues and classmates. Although the picture that emerges from the Person Network does not correspond exactly with people's real-life social networks (as the actual level of contact between network members is unknown and the Person Network does not include all relationships), it nonetheless has great research potential, particularly because of its scope: it covers the entire Dutch population, which makes it unique worldwide. Consequently, this network has already been used extensively (see, for example, Posthumus et al. 2020, Bos et al. 2022, and the POPNET project). With support of ODISSEI, this network file was also made available through the Remote-Access environment of the CBS.

Further development of the Person Network

As part of its innovation agenda, Statistics Netherlands in 2022 launched a project to further develop the Person Network. In this project, all network layers have been improved and expanded. An overview of all the changes compared to the earlier version of the Person Network can be found [here](#). Below, we will briefly discuss the two main expansions

in the Person Network, which concern the family members and the neighbours network layers.

In the previous version, the family members network layer comprised parents, children, siblings, cousins, nephews and nieces, uncles and aunts, grandparents and grandchildren. In the new version, the members of the step family and in-laws have been added to this network layer. People's step family and in-laws are relevant to many areas of social science research, such as the field of family sociology.

In the previous version, the neighbours network layer comprised the members of the 10 nearest households within a radius of 50 metres. However, this definition created a multitude of tiny clusters (Van der Laan et al. 2023), both in the countryside and in cities. This seemed undesirable, because in a real-life neighbours network, one would actually expect to find as you go through the network that people indirectly have ties with many other people. Therefore, it was decided to apply a new approach by breaking down the neighbours layer into two groups of relations: 'neighbours' and 'neighbourhood members'.

The new 'neighbours' group comprises all persons residing at the 10 nearest addresses, without any radius restriction being applied. As a result of this change, all people living in very rural areas have now also been assigned neighbours in the Person Network. Previously, this was quite often not the case in the first version of the Person Network due to the longer distances between households in these areas. The new 'neighbourhood members' group comprises 20 randomly selected people living within a 200-metre radius of the ego's home address. Particularly in very densely built-up areas, such as areas with many flats, including only the 10 nearest addresses often provided too little information about the neighbourhood in general.

The new subdivision of the neighbours layer is an improvement for many types of research. In rural areas, the nearest neighbour, even though this person lives relatively far away, may be more important to a person's social network than a neighbour would be in a densely populated area. In addition, neighbourhood members also provide a general picture of a person's immediate residential area and the people they encounter in the street. This can also be relevant for many types of research. The characteristics of this new neighbours network are now also more in line with the intuitive conception of such networks, as there are far fewer clusters (see Table 1).

Table 1. Network sizes of the five network layers, 2020

Layer	Number of persons	Number of links	Clustering coefficient	Number of components	Number of components comprising one person	Average size of components ¹	Median degree
Family members	16.8 mln	416.5 mln	0.45	886,894	557,751	14,442,893	19
Household members	14.8 mln	68.0 mln	1	7,625,605	2,597,347	6	2
Neighbours	17.3 mln	754.4 mln	0.19	126,477	126,287	15,893,072	44
Classmates	3.7 mln	282.3 mln	1	13,809,683	13,668,957	77	43
Colleagues	8.4 mln	679.8 mln	0.58	9,065,643	8,993,929	7,927,159	100

1. Only applies to components consisting of more than one person; weighted average, weighted proportionally to the size of the component

In addition to improving the definition of the network layers in the Person Network, Statistics Netherlands created a network time series running from 2009 through to 2022 (Dutch population as of 1 January), to which a new year will be added annually and which is available within Statistics Netherlands' remote access environment. This time series adds a wealth of opportunities for longitudinal research, such as research into nationwide or local developments in network measures, research into the network's (causal) influence on life course outcomes, or research into the distribution of all kinds of characteristics and behaviours across the network.

Application of Person Network in research into segregation

One of the key areas of application of Statistics Netherlands' Person Network is research into segregation. Usually only one dimension of segregation is analysed in such research, with most studies looking at residential segregation (Massey & Denton 1988; Musterd & Ostendorf 2009), or school segregation (Reardon & Owens 2014; Dronkers & Levels 2007). A multidimensional picture of segregation can add a great deal of insight. Segregation plays a role in all kinds of day-to-day contexts: within families, in school and at work. Furthermore, network analyses can have considerable added value, as from a theoretical perspective, segregation can be considered a network problem. Social network analysis addresses the question of how information is transferred in a social network. This

concerns information in the broadest sense of the word: opinions, values and norms and role models, but also more objective forms of information and knowledge, such as in relation to job openings, health, vaccines and education.

This transfer is influenced not only by direct but also by indirect relationships. When information is passed on to people indirectly through their social network, this facilitates integration and prevents the forming of 'social bubbles'. This is why a high level of segregation is considered undesirable: when there is no contact whatsoever between people, this impedes the spread of information from one social group to another. This can breed polarisation. Segregation can be based on all kinds of characteristics, but one of the most widely researched and socially relevant of these is social status.

Based on the time series for its Person Network, Statistics Netherlands published a [dashboard](#) this year on segregation based on education level with respect to people aged 25 to 55. This dashboard shows to what extent people with the same education level cluster in networks. Education level is a key indicator of social status. In the dashboard, segregation is measured by means of a random walk, with each link corresponding to one step in the random walk. People who are one step removed from the ego are weighted more heavily in the segregation score than people two steps removed, people three steps removed get an even smaller weight, and so on (Ballester & Vorsatz 2014). In addition, the segregation score is adjusted for the size of the different groups in the ego's geographical environment (within a 30-kilometre radius). If this adjustment were to be omitted, the segregation score would only reveal the well-known regional distribution of education levels (people with higher education mainly live in urban areas, which means their networks are by definition significantly clustered in urban areas). By contrast, the segregation score applied by Statistics Netherlands shows to what extent the different education level groups cluster within networks, on top of the well-known regional distribution across the country. More information about the calculation of the segregation score can be found in Van der Laan et al. 2023 and in the dashboard.

The dashboard is based on a categorisation into four education levels: low (people without a starting qualification and at most a VMBO diploma (prevocational secondary education) or a level 1 MBO diploma (secondary vocational education); midlevel (people with a level 2, 3 or 4 MBO diploma; Bachelor's degree (from a university of applied sciences (HBO) or research university); and Master's degree (from a university of applied sciences or research university). A segregation score of 0 means there is no segregation whatsoever; a score of 1 designates the maximum level of segregation. The dashboard shows that the segregation of people with a low education level decreased between 2009 and 2020. In 2009, those with

a low education level more often had people with the same education level in their network than was the case for any of the other education level groups. In 2020, that was no longer the case and people with a low education level were less segregated than those with a Master's degree or a midlevel education. That year, the group with a Master's degree was the most segregated, while the group with a Bachelor's degree was the least segregated (Statistics Netherlands, 2023).

Based on these figures it cannot be determined whether the change in education-based segregation is due to increased mixing of individuals within networks in recent years, or due to a change in group composition. The composition of the groups has changed over the years due to the inflow of new individuals who reached the age of 25 and the outflow of those who passed the age of 55. In addition, people may have attained a higher education level over the years and thus been assigned to another group.

The dashboard also provides insight into the level of segregation in each municipality. For example, in the four biggest cities (Amsterdam, Rotterdam, the Hague and Utrecht, Figure 1), education-based segregation exceeds the nationwide average. In these cities, particularly those with low education and those with a Master's degree are more segregated than is the case nationwide. It is often claimed that Dutch society is becoming increasingly segregated. When it comes to education-based segregation, that claim is not supported by these figures. The dashboard can serve as a tool for local policymakers by helping them to gain more insight into the development of the level of segregation in their municipality.

Figure 1. Education-based segregation in the Netherlands nationwide and in the four biggest cities

Privacy

Statistics Netherlands takes numerous measures to guarantee data privacy, starting with pseudonymisation. This means that the data do not contain any information by reference to which individuals could be identified, such as individuals' names, civil service numbers or addresses. The data can and may be used exclusively for the purposes of scientific research or compiling statistics, and are thus never used for the identification or detection of individuals. This is laid down in the [Statistics Netherlands Act \(CBS-wet\)](#). Statistics Netherlands exclusively conducts research into groups and never into individuals.

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